

Deliverable No. 4.2

Catalogue of training materials

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Partners

SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the GenderSAFE Catalogue of training materials, developed under Work Package 4 – Training. The catalogue brings together the main training packages, scripts, presentations and supporting documents prepared or adapted by GenderSAFE trainers to support capacity-building on gender-based violence in higher education and research.

The materials aim to support trainers, institutional change agents and other relevant actors in designing and delivering training sessions on effective institutional responses to gender-based violence. They cover introductory and thematic topics, different training formats and several language versions, in line with the objectives of Work Package 4.

The catalogue includes materials developed from the UniSAFE capacity-building programme and further adapted under GenderSAFE. It also includes new or updated materials developed through the project's training programme, Community of Practice activities and exchanges with trainers and participants.

The document is structured around three main sections. The first section introduces the purpose and scope of the deliverable. The second section explains how the materials were developed, reviewed and adapted. The third section presents the catalogue of training materials, including their content, format, target audience, language versions and supporting files.

By making these resources available, GenderSAFE aims to support the wider uptake of practical training on gender-based violence in academia. The catalogue is designed as a useful reference for trainers and institutions that wish to reuse, adapt or further develop the materials in their context.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation
7P	Prevalence, Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of services, Partnerships and Policies
D4.2	Deliverable 4.2
EU	European Union
GE Academy	Gender Equality Academy
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
PDF	Portable Document Format
PU	Public
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

GenderSAFE supports higher education institutions and research organisations in strengthening their institutional responses to gender-based violence. Capacity-building is an important part of this work, as effective action requires shared knowledge, practical tools and clear roles across the institution.

Work Package 4 focuses on training and capacity-building. It supports the development of skills and resources for those involved in preventing and addressing gender-based violence in academic and research settings. The training activities carried out under this work package addressed different audiences, including gender equality officers, trainers, ombudspersons, support actors, students, researchers, managers and other members of institutional communities.

This deliverable, **D4.2 Catalogue of Training Materials**, brings together the training materials developed, adapted and translated through these activities. Its purpose is to make the materials easier to access and use. The catalogue does not reproduce the full scripts. Instead, it provides a short overview of each training package and directs readers to the full materials. The authorship indicated for this deliverable refers to the preparation and editing of the catalogue as a whole. The authorship of each training package is included within the respective training package and may differ from the deliverable authorship.

The materials build on [GenderSAFE](#) work and, where relevant, on resources developed in the [UniSAFE](#) project. They respond to different training needs, from introductory knowledge on gender-based violence and the [7P framework](#) to more focused topics such as active bystander intervention, resistance, strategic framing and participatory policy development.

The training materials can be adapted to different national, institutional and audience contexts. Trainers are encouraged to adjust examples, exercises, timing and references as needed, while keeping the GenderSAFE attribution and respecting the licence terms.

1.1 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This deliverable is organised in three main chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the purpose of the catalogue, its intended audience and how the training packages can be used. Chapter 2 briefly explains how the materials were developed, tested and refined. Chapter 3 presents the catalogue of training materials.

Each catalogue entry follows the same structure: title, description, learning objectives, profile of participants, duration, format and language. Each entry also includes a link to download the related training materials.

1.2 INTENDED AUDIENCE

This catalogue is intended for trainers, gender equality officers, institutional change agents and other professionals working to prevent and address gender-based violence in higher education and research. It may also be useful for ombudspersons, trusted persons, human resources staff, student support actors, managers, researchers and students involved in institutional policy work or capacity-building and anyone interested in addressing gender-based violence in research and academia.

1.3 HOW TO USE A GENDERSAFE TRAINING PACKAGE

Each training package includes introductory information to help trainers understand the purpose and scope of the session. This usually includes the title, description, learning objectives, profile of

participants, duration, format and language. The full scripts provide a detailed training structure with suggested timing, methods, exercises and facilitation notes. Trainers are encouraged to review the full package before delivery and adapt the examples, timing and exercises to their own context, audience and level of experience. Where supporting materials are provided, such as worksheets, case stories, Miro templates or role-playing scenarios, these should be prepared in advance and adapted where needed. Users should also check whether legal, institutional or support-related references need to be updated for their national or organisational context.

1.4 LICENSING TERMS

The GenderSAFE training materials are made available for reuse and adaptation under the [Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/) (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0).

This means that the materials may be used and adapted for non-commercial purposes, provided that appropriate credit is given, the GenderSAFE attribution is kept and any adapted versions are shared under the same licence terms. When adapting the materials, users should also keep the citation included in each training package and clearly indicate where changes have been made. This helps ensure that the materials remain open, reusable and properly credited.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF THE TRAINING MATERIALS

The training materials presented in this catalogue were developed under GenderSAFE Work Package 4, which focuses on training and capacity-building. They build on training sessions and workshops delivered through the project, as well as on resources and knowledge developed under UniSAFE¹.

UniSAFE provided an important basis for the materials. Several training packages draw on the UniSAFE 7P framework, the [UniSAFE Toolkit](#)², survey findings, policy guidance, case stories, persona stories and practical resources for addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research. GenderSAFE further developed this basis by adapting the materials to new training needs, including support for institutional policy development, testing the [GenderSAFE Model Policy Framework for addressing gender-based violence](#), active bystander intervention, resistance to change and strategic framing.

The development process was also informed by pedagogical principles for gender equality training, including the GE Academy quality standards³. These principles guided the design of the materials, with attention to clear learning objectives, appropriate methods, the profile of participants, participatory learning and the link between training and institutional change.

Because the materials address gender-based violence, particular attention was given to creating a safe⁴ and respectful learning environment. The scripts include guidance on confidentiality, ground rules, trigger warnings, the possibility for participants to step out if needed and the importance of not requiring personal disclosures. This approach is also supported by the guidance document on creating a safe space for discussion and dialogue in training sessions on gender-based violence.

The materials were first prepared as scripts, PowerPoint presentations and supporting resources for specific GenderSAFE sessions. After delivery, trainers worked with Yellow Window to review and improve them. These feedback loops helped refine timing, clarify instructions, adjust exercises, improve examples and make the materials easier for other trainers to use.

Several training packages were also translated and adapted to different language and national contexts. These versions were not treated as direct translations only, but as contextualised materials that may reflect different legal, institutional and linguistic settings.

The final training packages are designed to be adaptable. Trainers may adjust examples, timing, exercises and references to their own context, while keeping the GenderSAFE attribution and respecting the licence terms.

¹ UniSAFE was an EU-funded project that produced evidence on gender-based violence and sexual harassment in research organisations and translated this knowledge into practical tools for higher education institutions, research organisations and policymakers.

² The UniSAFE Toolkit is particularly relevant, as it supports higher education institutions and research organisations in addressing gender-based violence, whether they are starting to work on the issue, designing a policy or improving existing institutional measures.

³ The development of the GenderSAFE training materials was informed by the GE Academy quality standards for gender equality training. These standards were developed to support the design and delivery of high-quality training activities on gender equality and institutional change in research and higher education. They provide guidance on defining clear learning objectives, selecting appropriate methods, adapting training to participants' profiles and using participatory approaches that support reflection and practical learning. Link to the document, [here](#).

⁴ Creating a safe space for discussion and dialogue in a training session on gender-based violence (online & offline): For an effective training session, it is important to ensure that participants feel comfortable, respected and supported throughout the training, preventing re-traumatising and triggering of the participants. This guide provides some practical tips for trainers and change agents. Download the guide, [here](#).

3. CATALOGUE OF TRAINING MATERIALS

The table below presents the training materials currently available under the GenderSAFE capacity-building programme.

No.	Training material	Format	Language version(s)
1	Introductory training on gender-based violence in academia and the 7P framework	Online	English, Greek, French, Czech, Italian, Spanish and Portuguese
2	Addressing gender-based violence in academia using the 7P framework: training for ombudspersons and institutional support actors	In-person	English
3	Addressing gender-based violence against trans and non-binary people in universities and academia	Online	English
4	Active bystander intervention	In-person	English
5	Overcoming resistance in gender-based violence policy-making	In-person	English
6	Participatory techniques for testing the Model Policy Framework	Online	English
7	Strategic framing for testing the Model Policy Framework	Online	English
8	Students as agents of change: addressing gender-based violence in higher education	Online	English
9	Training of Trainers	Online	English
10	Strengthening individual and institutional competencies in the area of social safety	Online	Czech
11	Participatory techniques for policy development on gender-based violence	In-person	English

In addition to the training packages listed above, the catalogue includes a set of complementary resources developed through the same capacity-building work. These resources are included in this section because they support the delivery, adaptation and evaluation of the training materials. They are not stand-alone training sessions, but they can be used across different trainings and institutional contexts:

No.	Complementary material	Type	Language version(s)
12	Co-creation and participatory approaches towards addressing gender-based violence in research and academia	Guide	English
13	Strategic framing to tackle resistance to change: Addressing gender-based violence in research and academia	Guide	English
14	GenderSAFE exit questionnaire	Evaluation material	English, adaptable to the training language

3.1 INTRODUCTORY TRAINING ON GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN ACADEMIA AND THE 7P FRAMEWORK

Description: This training introduces participants to gender-based violence in academic and research settings. It provides a common understanding of key concepts, the impact of gender-based violence in academia and the specific features of the phenomenon in higher education institutions and research organisations. The training presents the UniSAFE 7P model — Prevalence, Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of services, Partnerships and Policies — as a holistic framework for institutional action. It also shares inspiring practices from European higher education institutions and research organisations that have developed and implemented policies to address gender-based violence.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- gain a common understanding of concepts related to gender-based violence and understand its impact in academia
- demonstrate the existence of gender-based violence in the research field and highlight its specific features in academic settings
- present the UniSAFE 7P model as a holistic approach to addressing gender-based violence in higher education institutions and research organisations
- share inspiring practices for setting up and implementing institutional policies to address gender-based violence in academia

Profile of participants

This training is designed for gender equality officers or focal points, equality and diversity officers, human resources officers, Gender Equality Plan implementing teams, health and safety officers, heads of departments or units involved in gender-based violence prevention and response and trainers working on gender-based violence in academic settings. The training is particularly relevant for participants who are at the beginning stages of creating and implementing a policy framework to address gender-based violence in academia.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 9–25

Format: Online, adaptable to in-person delivery

Duration: 5.5 hours, including breaks

Language: English, Greek, French, Czech, Italian, Spanish and Portuguese

[Download the training materials in English here](#)

[Download the training materials in Greek here](#)

[Download the training materials in French here](#)

[Download the training materials in Czech here](#)

[Download the training materials in Italian here](#)

[Download the training materials in Spanish here](#)

[Download the training materials in Portuguese here](#)

3.2 ADDRESSING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN ACADEMIA USING THE 7P FRAMEWORK: TRAINING FOR OMBUDSPERSONS AND INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT ACTORS

Description: This training introduces participants to gender-based violence in higher education and research, with a focus on institutional responses and the role of support actors. It presents gender-based violence as a continuum of behaviours, ranging from subtle and normalised forms of misconduct to more severe forms of violence. The training also explores how power relations, hierarchy, dependency and intersecting inequalities shape both the experience of violence and the ability to report it. It uses the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE 7P framework to support participants in understanding how institutions can address gender-based violence through connected measures on prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution and disciplinary measures, provision of services, partnerships and policies.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- define and recognise different forms of gender-based violence in higher education and research
- understand gender-based violence as a continuum, rooted in power relations and intersecting inequalities
- explore key factors that enable gender-based violence in academic settings, including hierarchy, dependency, institutional culture and underreporting
- present the UniSAFE and GenderSAFE 7P framework as a holistic approach to address gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations
- introduce relevant policy and institutional frameworks, including the GenderSAFE Model Policy Framework
- reflect on prevention measures, including awareness-raising campaigns, bystander intervention, active consent training and red flag systems

Profile of participants

This training is designed for ombudspersons and members of ombuds networks, trusted persons and first responders, gender equality officers, focal points and diversity officers, human resources officers, Gender Equality Plan teams, health and safety officers, student support and wellbeing staff, members of complaint-handling, investigation or disciplinary bodies, heads of departments or units involved in prevention or response and trainers working on gender-based violence in academic settings. The training is particularly relevant for participants who already have an institutional role in prevention, support, reporting or policy implementation. It does not require advanced prior knowledge of gender-based violence.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 8–25

Format: In-person

Duration: 4 hours, including breaks

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.3 ADDRESSING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE AGAINST TRANS AND NON-BINARY PEOPLE IN UNIVERSITIES AND ACADEMIA

Description: This training focuses on gender-based violence against trans and non-binary people in universities and research organisations. It introduces key concepts related to trans and non-binary identities, cisnormativity, the gender binary and the continuum of gender-based violence. The training also explores how cisnormativity and intersecting inequalities shape experiences of violence, exclusion, reporting and access to support in academic settings. It includes a case-based group exercise where participants analyse gender-based violence against a trans or non-binary person and reflect on root causes, institutional factors and consequences.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- understand the definitions and scope of gender-based violence, including the concept of the continuum of violence, its prevalence and impact in a university context
- learn about cisnormativity and the gender binary in relation to gender-based violence
- understand the importance of an inclusive environment for trans and non-binary people in universities
- develop skills in handling offensive comments and behaviour in university settings, where the optional exercise is used

Profile of participants

This training is designed for educators and teachers, gender equality officers or focal points, equality and diversity officers, human resources officers, Gender Equality Plan implementing teams, health and safety officers, heads of departments or units involved in gender-based violence prevention and response and trainers working on gender-based violence in academic settings.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 9–25

Format: Online

Duration: 2 hours, including breaks, with an optional additional 1.5-hour exercise and 1-hour lunch break

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.4 ACTIVE BYSTANDER INTERVENTION

Description: This training introduces active bystander intervention as a practical approach to recognising and responding to gender-based violence in higher education and research settings. It supports participants to identify situations where intervention may be needed, reflect on barriers to intervention and practise safe responses using the 5D model developed by [Right To Be](#). The training includes interactive exercises, examples from the continuum of gender-based violence, role-playing and group discussion.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- articulate the forms of gender-based violence
- understand the responsibility of bystanders and possible effects of intervening
- build awareness of situations where bystander intervention may be appropriate or needed
- learn about the 5D intervention model designed by Right To Be
- practise safe intervention strategies through role-playing and discussion

Profile of participants

This training is designed for administrative staff, faculty members, researchers, students and members of higher education institutions and research organisations who wish to be empowered as active bystanders and take action against gender-based violence by intervening in (potentially) harmful situations.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 9–50

Format: In-person

Duration: 3 hours, including breaks

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.5 OVERCOMING RESISTANCE IN GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE POLICY-MAKING

Description: This training supports participants in recognising and responding to resistance that may arise when developing, implementing or strengthening policies to address gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations. Resistance may appear as open opposition, dismissive comments, denial of the problem, delays, lack of prioritisation, refusal to take responsibility, procedural blocking or backlash against those working for change. The training combines a conceptual introduction, personal reflection, a World Café exercise based on resistance scenarios and practical work on self-care and action planning.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- strengthen participants' understanding of how resistance to gender equality and gender-based violence policy work can manifest in institutional settings
- support participants in recognising active, passive, individual, group and institutional forms of resistance
- identify and discuss practical strategies to prepare for, respond to and follow up on resistance
- strengthen the understanding that resistance can be a sign that institutional change work is having an effect
- support participants' confidence, self-care and sense of agency when facing resistance in their everyday work

Profile of participants

This training is designed for people involved in developing, implementing or supporting institutional policies and measures to address gender-based violence in higher education and research settings. It is relevant for gender equality officers, equality and diversity officers, Gender Equality Plan teams, human resources staff, ombudspersons, trusted persons, institutional support actors, staff involved in policy development, ethics, legal affairs, student support or staff wellbeing, managers, trainers, researchers, students and staff representatives involved in institutional change.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 20–35

Format: In-person, adaptable to online delivery

Duration: 3.5 hours, including a break

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.6 PARTICIPATORY TECHNIQUES FOR TESTING THE MODEL POLICY FRAMEWORK

Description: This workshop introduces participatory techniques that can support institutions in testing selected parts of the GenderSAFE Model Policy Framework. It is designed for institutions, teams and professionals who wish to use participatory techniques to test, adapt or further develop policies for addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research settings. The workshop focuses on stakeholder mapping and journey mapping as practical tools to identify relevant actors, clarify institutional steps and plan a realistic testing process.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this workshop are to:

- offer participants a clear overview of the GenderSAFE Model Policy Framework and support them in selecting the parts they wish to test in their institutions
- introduce participatory techniques that can support the testing process, with a focus on stakeholder mapping and journey mapping
- equip participants with practical skills to identify relevant stakeholders, potential allies, sources of resistance and decision-making roles in their institutions
- support participants in planning the sequence of steps needed to test selected parts of the Model Policy Framework, including consultation, co-creation, drafting, advocacy and formal approval

Profile of participants

This workshop is designed for people involved in testing, adapting or further developing policies to address gender-based violence in higher education and research. It is relevant for institutional teams supporting policy development, gender equality officers, equality and diversity officers, human resources staff, legal officers, student support actors, ombudspersons, institutional change agents and allies who can support consultation, co-creation, drafting, advocacy or approval processes.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 10–25

Format: Online

Duration: 2.5 hours, including a break

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.7 STRATEGIC FRAMING FOR TESTING THE MODEL POLICY FRAMEWORK

Description: This workshop introduces strategic framing as a practical approach for strengthening institutional policy work on gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations. Institutional change is rarely achieved through good arguments alone. Change agents often work with limited power, limited resources, competing priorities and different forms of resistance. Strategic framing helps them connect policy goals to the concerns, values and responsibilities of different stakeholders. The workshop combines a short conceptual introduction with two hands-on exercises on crafting tailored messages and refining responses to possible resistance.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this workshop are to:

- build participants' capacity to use strategic framing when advocating for institutional responses to gender-based violence in higher education and research
- support participants in aligning messages on gender-based violence with institutional values, priorities and concerns
- provide practical tools for crafting messages for different stakeholder groups, including stakeholders who may be hesitant or resistant
- support participants in anticipating possible resistance and preparing realistic responses
- help participants integrate strategic framing into policy development, negotiation and implementation processes

Profile of participants

This workshop is designed for people involved in developing, adapting, implementing or advocating for institutional policies and measures to address gender-based violence in higher education and research. It is relevant for gender equality officers, equality and diversity officers, Gender Equality Plan teams, human resources staff, legal officers, ombudspersons, complaints office staff, student support services, staff wellbeing services, safeguarding actors, managers, researchers, students, staff representatives and trainers working on institutional policy work.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 10–25

Format: Online, adaptable to in-person or hybrid delivery

Duration: 2.5 hours, including a break

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.8 STUDENTS AS AGENTS OF CHANGE: ADDRESSING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Description: This training introduces students to the issue of gender-based violence in higher education and explores how they can contribute to institutional change. It provides an overview of key concepts, the continuum of violence in academia and the UniSAFE 7P framework, which covers Prevalence, Prevention, Protection, Prosecution, Provision of services, Partnerships and Policies. The training focuses on the role of students as agents of change and invites participants to reflect on how students can contribute to awareness-raising, advocacy, peer support, policy engagement and dialogue with institutional actors. Through interactive activities and group discussion, participants explore practical ways to recognise gaps, mobilise student communities and support safer and more inclusive academic environments.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- understand gender-based violence and the continuum of violence in academia
- become familiar with the UniSAFE 7P framework as a holistic approach to addressing gender-based violence in higher education and research
- identify different roles that students can play in addressing gender-based violence, including awareness-raising, advocacy, peer support, policy engagement and coalition-building
- reflect on how students can contribute to institutional change in their own contexts
- leave the session with at least one concrete takeaway, action idea or next step relevant to their institution or student community

Profile of participants

This training is designed for students of any level, including Bachelor, Master and PhD students across Europe. It is particularly relevant for students who are interested in gender-based violence and institutional change, active or interested in student organisations, unions or networks, involved in equality, diversity, inclusion or student wellbeing initiatives or motivated to contribute to change within their institution. Participants do not need to be experts on gender-based violence, but they should be interested in contributing to safer and more inclusive higher education environments.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 9–30

Format: Online

Duration: 3 hours, including a 30-minute break

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.9 TRAINING OF TRAINERS

Description: This Training of Trainers supports participants in developing the knowledge, skills and confidence needed to deliver training on gender-based violence in research and academia. It builds on methodologies and insights from the GE Academy, UniSAFE and GenderSAFE projects, combining conceptual input, practical tools and participatory feminist methodologies. The training introduces participants to the UniSAFE 7P framework and the available UniSAFE and GenderSAFE capacity-building materials. It also supports participants to work with training scripts, case stories, persona stories, journey maps, the Lotus Blossom technique and other participatory tools that can be adapted to different institutional and national contexts. The programme is designed as an experiential learning process, where participants reflect on their own training experience, practise facilitation techniques, design short training sessions and receive feedback from trainers and peers.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- develop training capacity and gain expertise to adapt and facilitate training sessions on addressing gender-based violence in research and academia
- apply gender training methodologies and tools for designing and delivering participatory training sessions
- use training scripts and supporting materials developed through UniSAFE and GenderSAFE
- create a safe space for discussion and dialogue in training sessions on gender-based violence
- apply quality standards in gender training, drawing on the Gender Equality Academy principles and with a specific focus on gender-based violence

Profile of participants

This training is designed for participants who are expected to deliver, adapt or support training on gender-based violence in research and academia. It is relevant for gender equality officers or focal points, equality, diversity and inclusion officers, members of Gender Equality Plan implementation teams, trainers and facilitators working on gender equality or gender-based violence, researchers or project partners involved in institutional change processes, ombudspersons, trusted persons, support actors and members of higher education institutions and research organisations who are expected to use or adapt UniSAFE and GenderSAFE training materials. Participants should have a basic understanding of gender equality and an interest in addressing gender-based violence in academic and research settings. Previous training experience is useful, but not required.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: Small group format recommended

Format: Online

Duration: 12 hours, delivered over three afternoons of 4 hours each

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.10 STRENGTHENING INDIVIDUAL AND INSTITUTIONAL COMPETENCIES IN THE AREA OF SOCIAL SAFETY

Description: This online training focuses on strengthening individual and institutional competencies in the area of social safety in academic settings. It offers practical approaches to building a culture of safety, responsibility and trust when addressing gender-based violence and other forms of harmful behaviour. The training is structured around three thematic blocks: active bystander intervention, communication strategies to overcome distrust and internal regulation as a tool for establishing formal procedures for handling concerns and cases.

Learning objectives

The main objectives of this training are to:

- understand the complexity and specific features of gender-based violence and social safety in academic settings
- understand the principles of active bystander intervention and practise how they can be applied in situations involving gender-based violence
- become familiar with communication strategies that can help overcome distrust towards social safety mechanisms and institutional support systems
- understand the role of internal regulation as a tool for setting clear and formal procedures for handling cases and concerns
- create space for exchange, mutual learning and reflection on how institutional measures can be strengthened

Profile of participants

This training is designed for people who are involved in developing, implementing or strengthening measures related to social safety, gender equality, prevention of gender-based violence or safe and respectful working and learning environments in academic and research institutions. It is relevant for gender equality and diversity officers, Gender Equality Plan teams, ombudspersons, trusted persons, contact points, human resources staff, legal staff, student support actors, communication staff, managers and people involved in preparing, revising or implementing internal regulations and procedures.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 10–25

Format: Online

Duration: 4 hours, including a break

Language: Czech

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.11 PARTICIPATORY TECHNIQUES FOR POLICY DEVELOPMENT ON GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

Description: This hands-on training introduces participatory techniques that can support the development, review and implementation of institutional policies on gender-based violence in higher education and research organisations. Participants explore how tools such as journey maps, persona stories and the Lotus Blossom technique can be used to open structured discussions, identify gaps in institutional responses and support the co-creation of more effective policies. The training focuses on practical application and gives participants the opportunity to test the tools through group exercises.

Learning objectives

The main objective of this training is to support participants in using participatory techniques for the design, review and improvement of institutional policies addressing gender-based violence.

By the end of the training, participants will be able to:

- understand how participatory techniques can support policy development and implementation on gender-based violence
- identify when to use tools such as journey maps, persona stories and Lotus Blossom exercises
- use persona stories to explore how institutional policies and procedures may affect different people
- apply journey mapping to identify institutional touchpoints, gaps, challenges and opportunities
- use the Lotus Blossom technique to explore problems and develop possible actions or interventions
- reflect on how participatory methods can strengthen stakeholder engagement in policy-making

Profile of participants

This training is designed for people involved in developing, reviewing or implementing policies and procedures on gender-based violence in higher education and research settings. It is relevant for gender equality officers, equality and diversity officers, Gender Equality Plan teams, human resources staff, legal officers, ombudspersons, institutional support actors, student support services, safeguarding actors, complaints office staff, managers, trainers, researchers, students and staff representatives involved in policy development or institutional change.

Duration and format

Recommended number of participants: 20–35

Format: In-person

Duration: 3 hours, including a break

Language: English

[Download the training materials here](#)

3.12 CO-CREATION AND PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES TOWARDS ADDRESSING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN RESEARCH AND ACADEMIA

Title: Co-creation and participatory approaches towards addressing gender-based violence in research and academia

Description: This guide supports the use of co-creation and participatory techniques in policy work on gender-based violence in research and academia. It explains how participatory methods can help institutions gather input from different stakeholders, support dialogue and develop more inclusive and sustainable policies. The guide presents practical tools such as persona stories, journey maps, Lotus Blossom, stakeholder mapping, cause diagrams, World Café and SWOT analysis.

Purpose: The guide can be used by trainers, facilitators and institutional change agents who want to design participatory workshops, support policy development or involve stakeholders in discussions on gender-based violence. It is also a useful supporting resource for the training packages on participatory techniques.

Format and language:

Format: PDF guide

Language: English

[Download the resource here](#)

3.13 STRATEGIC FRAMING TO TACKLE RESISTANCE TO CHANGE: ADDRESSING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE IN RESEARCH AND ACADEMIA

Description: This guide supports change agents in responding to resistance when working on institutional policies and measures to address gender-based violence. It brings together common arguments that minimise, dismiss or deflect the need for action and offers possible responses grounded in evidence, institutional responsibility and shared values. The guide is based on materials co-created within GenderSAFE and draws on insights from project workshops and training sessions.

Purpose: The guide can be used by trainers, equality officers, institutional change agents and others who need to communicate about gender-based violence in a clear and strategic way. It is particularly useful when preparing for policy discussions, training sessions, advocacy meetings or conversations with resistant stakeholders.

Format and language:

Format: PDF guide

Language: English

[Download the resource here](#)

3.14 GENDERSAFE EXIT QUESTIONNAIRE

Description: The GenderSAFE exit questionnaire is an evaluation tool recommended for use at the end of training sessions, workshops and webinars. It helps trainers collect participants' feedback on the content, methods, facilitation and overall usefulness of the session.

The questionnaire is designed to be adapted to each training session. Trainers can adjust the questions according to the specific learning objectives, format and target group of the training delivered.

Purpose: The exit questionnaire supports the review and improvement of the training materials. Feedback collected through the questionnaire can help trainers assess whether the learning objectives were met and identify possible improvements to the timing, exercises, examples, instructions and supporting resources.

Format and language:

Format: Online questionnaire / template

Language: English, adaptable to the language of the training

[Download the exit questionnaire template here](#)

CLOSING NOTE

The training materials presented in this catalogue are intended to support the continued delivery, adaptation and uptake of capacity-building activities on gender-based violence in higher education and research. Building on UniSAFE and further adapted, expanded and contextualised under GenderSAFE, they provide trainers, institutional change agents and other relevant actors with practical resources for designing and facilitating training sessions in different settings.

Each training package includes guidance on learning objectives, format, duration, target audience, participant preparation and facilitation, together with adaptable templates and supporting materials where relevant. The materials are designed to be flexible and can be tailored to different national, institutional and audience contexts, while preserving the core messages, GenderSAFE attribution and applicable licence terms.

By bringing these resources together, D4.2 contributes to the sustainability of the GenderSAFE capacity-building programme and supports the wider use of shared, high-quality training materials across institutions committed to preventing and addressing gender-based violence in academia. Users who adapt, translate or further develop the materials are encouraged to keep the GenderSAFE team informed and may contact the project at training@gendersafe.eu.